

Reasoning Ability, Emotional Intelligence and Memory-Capacity as Predictors of Academic Achievement among Chemistry Students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity as predictors of academic achievement among chemistry students in colleges of education in north-central geo-political zone, Nigeria using some selected Colleges of Educations in the North Central geo-political Zone, a sample of Three hundred and twenty-eight (328) 200 level chemistry students were selected for the study using simple random sampling. Correlation survey research design was adopted for the study. Three instruments used were adapted and validated; these are Meta-memory in Adulthood Questionnaire (MIA), Trait Emotional Intelligent Questionnaire (TEIQ) and Group Assessment for Logical Thinking (GALT) with reliability coefficients of 0.81, 0.84 and 0.86. Three research questions were investigated and were analyzed using descriptive statistics of Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) while the three null hypotheses were tested at $p \leq 0.05$. Major findings of the study shows that, reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity with p -values of 0.00, 0.01 and 0.01 that are less than 0.05 are all good predictors of academic performance, while reasoning ability is the most effective predictor, emotional intelligent is the least effective predictor. It is therefore recommended among others that students at various levels be exposed to reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity skill.

Keywords: reasoning ability, emotional intelligence, memory-capacity and academic performance

Reasoning Ability, Emotional Intelligence and Memory-Capacity as Predictors of Academic Achievement among Chemistry Students in Colleges Of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria

Introduction

Chemistry is a subject of universal interest in human development with regards to the utility of its knowledge in real life situations. As the science that deals with composition, properties and uses of matter, Chemistry enables anyone who studies it to develop the skill of critical observation, experimentation, manipulation of variables, critical analysis as well as making deductions which are very important in the investigation of scientific processes. Its knowledge through its contents and process has enabled production of good drinking water, food, improved health care delivery through the production of drugs, materials for construction industries, roads and automobiles in our homes. Many household items are products of science and many of these items are produced from natural and synthetic compounds, which are principally organic molecules that are studied in Organic Chemistry.

Reasoning ability is something that your mind actually thinks why what and how. It is the ability to take the inputs from five memory organs process the data and give the relative solution. Reasoning is critical as its application is of crucial importance for advances in the sciences and mathematics, as the scientific method relies on heavily on deductive reasoning which enables individuals to raise premises and seek for solution. Dianne (2016) has attributed that reasoning ability can be used to predicts the performance of students' in chemistry. Piaget (1972) in his theory explains that, in concrete operational stage, students use concrete reasoning patterns in tackling problems. The reasoning patterns are applied to concrete objects or directly observable properties and simple relationship. Moreover, Johnson (2018) reported that students identified as the concrete operational students might have an inefficient working memory and difficulty in understanding concepts simultaneously. The results of Ertepmar (2015) and Cavallo (2016) from investigating the relationship between students' reasoning ability and their understanding of genetic topics shows that reasoning ability best predict students' achievement in solving genetic problems. They identified four basic reasoning skills: storage skills, retrieving skills, matching skills and execution skills. Oloyede (2018) found that formal reasoning ability is a strong predictor for the achievement in chemistry.

Emotional Intelligence is the ability of one to monitor his own and others feelings and emotions, discriminate among them and use the information to guide one's thinking and actions. Mari (2012)

simply puts emotional intelligence as learned ability to identify, understand, experience and express human emotions in healthy and productive ways. The ability to control the emotions has become important for the students not to get carried away by the flow of negative and evil elements. When a person becomes stressed he/she may tend to be over-emotional and allow emotions to influence decisions and relationship towards his study and study partners, so having a high emotional intelligence make the person cope with stress in a healthy way and keep emotions in check. A high emotional intelligence helps to maintain a state of harmony in oneself and finally be more self confident in dealing with challenges of living and learning in educational institutions. High emotional intelligence according to Johnson (2018) can contribute positively to a student learning process. Students with low emotional intelligence may find failure more difficult to deal with, which undermines their academic motivation. Memory- Capacity refers to individual difference construct reflecting the limited capacity of a person's working memory. It is also refers to as the ability to keep information current in mind for a short period, while using this information for the task at hand. Engle (2012) hypothesized that memory-capacity is about using attention to maintain or suppress information and that it is not really about storage but about the capacity to controlled, sustained attention in the face of interference or distraction. Study from Swanson (2016) shows that student with high working memory-capacity have advantage to perform better than student with low working memory-capacity. He maintained that working memory-capacity tasks, in which participants maintain information while completing a concurrent processing task are thought to index retention processes in the face of distraction and are also linked to wide variety of developing cognitive and academic skills and classroom behavior. Theoretically, the study was based on Piaget theory of reasoning which deals with cognitive development that explains how individual learn to think logically and reason scientifically, This theory is based on the idea that children's thinking and reasoning change in stages as they grow through four developmental stages: the sensorimotor stage, preoperational stage, concrete operational stage and formal operational stage. Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence which described emotional intelligence as a set of skills that can be learned and developed, which enabled individuals to recognize and understand emotions in themselves and others, and to use this awareness to guide thought and behavior and it consists of five components: Self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills. Badeley's theory of working memory capacity which

described working memory as a limited-capacity system that plays a crucial role in cognitive processes such as learning, problem-solving, and decision making. The key features of this theory are Limited capacity, multiple components, dynamic interactions, and importance of attention. It is against this background that this study attempts to examine the impact of reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity as predictors of academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central geo-political zone, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Chemistry as a subject, virtually affects all aspects of human life and it is a basic requirement for admission for nearly all the courses of study in the field of science in tertiary institutions. National Policy on Education (2014) placed chemistry on a prestigious position as a servicing subject to engineering, Medicine and computer science courses in the universities (Najdi, 2013). Nevertheless, the subject has not attained students' performance at its best. It is observed that most of the students from 100 to 300 levels in Colleges of Education would have several carryovers. As a result many of the students are withdrawn some spend more than the stipulated period for the completion of the course while some graduated with pass grade. This poor students' academic achievement in chemistry according to researcher is attributed to many factors such as teachers' factor, environmental factors, and students' factors. In the 21st century, there is a shift of focus from all the listed factors responsible to students' poor academic achievement to more influential students' factors such as reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity Ladipo (2023). For this reason, there is need to find out if reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity will correlate with students' achievement.

Research Questions

The following were the research questions for the study:

RQ₁: What is the relationship between reasoning ability and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

RQ₂: What is the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

RQ₃: What is the relationship between memory capacity and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following Null Hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between reasoning ability and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between memory capacity and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Research Methodology and Population of the Study

The research design adopted for this study is a descriptive survey research method. This method is preferred because it involves the use of questionnaire in order to determine the opinion and perception of participants on a particular concept. The population of this study consists of all Chemistry students' in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. Three hundred (300) participants were randomly selected across three Federal and three State Colleges of Education for the study.

Research Instruments

The instruments used for data collection are; Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQ), Group Assessment for Logical Thinking (GALT), Meta-memory in Adulthood Questionnaire (MIA) and CGPA of 200 level Chemistry students'.

Data analysis and Presentation of Results

Data obtained for the purpose of this study analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics based on the research questions and hypotheses formulated as follows:

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between reasoning ability and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

The data collected to answer research question one, was analyzed using Mean, Standard and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics (PPMCC) as shown in Table 4.1

Table 4.1 Pearson- Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Statistics on Relationship between Reasoning Ability and Academic Achievement in Chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	STD	r-value	Remark
Academic Achievement	328	2.39	0.75		There exist high positive relationship
Reasoning Ability	328	21.14	7.189	0.77**	

Table 4.1 reveals the r-value 0.77 between reasoning ability and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. The table shows a high positive relationship between the two variables; reasoning ability and academic achievement since the r- value is greater than 0.05.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

The data collected to answer research question one, was analyzed using Mean, Standard and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics (PPMCC) as shown in Table 4.2

Table 4.2: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Statistics on Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement in among Chemistry Students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	STD	r-value	Remark
Academic Achievement	328	2.39	0.75		There exist moderate positive relationship
Emotional Intelligence	328	103.39	23.71	0.48**	

Table 4.2 reveals the r-value of 0.48 and the r-value was not carrying the negative sign which means that there was a moderate positive correlation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. The table revealed a moderate positive relationship between the two variables. This according to Swanson (2016), r- value from 0.10 to 0.29 for low correlation, 0.30 to 0.49 for moderate correlation

and 0.50 to 1 for high correlation..

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between memory capacity and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria? The data collected to answer research question one, was analyzed using Mean, Standard and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics (PPMCC) as shown in Table 4.3

Table 4.3: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Statistics on Relationship between Memory-capacity and Academic Achievement in among Chemistry Students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	STD	r-value	Remark
Academic Achievement	328	2.39	0.75	0.63**	There exist high positive relationship
Memory-capacity	328	112.87	25.41		

Table 4.3 reveals the r-value 0.63 between memory-capacity and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. The table revealed a high positive relationship between the two variables; memory-capacity and academic achievement since the r- value was not carrying a negative sign and has a value greater than 0.05.

Hypotheses

The Hypotheses were tested with both Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and the Regression Analysis. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance

Hypotheses One: There is no significant relationship between reasoning ability and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Table 4.4: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Statistics On Relationship between Reasoning Ability and Academic Achievement in among Chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	STD	r-value	P-value	Remark
Academic Achievement	328	2.39	0.75	0.77	0.00	Sig
Reasoning Ability	328	21.14	7.19			

Alpha p value = 0.05 level of significance

Table 4.4 of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistics reveals p-value of 0.00 which is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. This showed that significant relationship exist between reasoning ability and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. Therefore the null hypothesis that stated that there is no significance relationship between Reasoning Ability and Academic Achievement among Chemistry Students in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria, is thereby rejected.

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Table 4.5: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Statistics on Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement in among Chemistry Students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	STD	r-value	P-value	Remark
Academic Achievement	328	2.39	0.75			
Reasoning Ability	328	21.14	7.189	0.048	0.01	Sig

Alpha p value = 0.05 level of significance

Table 4.5 of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistics reveals p-value of 0.01 which is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. This showed that significant relationship exist between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. Therefore the null hypothesis that stated that there is no significance relationship between emotional intelligence and Academic Achievement among Chemistry Students in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria, is thereby rejected.

Hypotheses Three: There is no significant relationship between memory capacity and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Table 4.6: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Statistics on Relationship between Memory-capacity and Academic Achievement in among Chemistry Students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	STD	r-value	P-value	Remark
Academic Achievement	328	2.39	0.75			
Memory-capacity	328	112.87	25.41	0.63	0.01	Sig

Table 4.6 of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistics reveals p-value of 0.01 which is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. This showed that significant relationship exist between reasoning ability and academic achievement among chemistry students in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. Therefore the null hypothesis that stated that there is no significance relationship between Reasoning Ability and Academic Achievement among Chemistry Students in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria, is hereby rejected.

Discussion of the Results

The study was conducted using correlation survey research design. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the Colleges. One hundred and fifty 200 level chemistry students constituted the sample. Three instruments were used for data collection; Meta-memory in Adulthood Questionnaire (MAQ) Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQ) and Group Assessment for Logical Thinking (GALT) with reliability coefficients of 0.86, 0.81 and 0.84 respectively. Data obtained were analyzed using SPSS statistical package (20. Version) and the findings indicated that reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity have positive significant correlation with academic achievement but with different impacts. All the P-values obtained: 0.00, 0.01 and 0.01 for reasoning ability, emotional intelligent and memory-capacity are lower than 0.05 alpha level of significance hence, significant relationship exist between reasoning ability, emotional intelligent, memory-capacity and students’ academic achievement. The findings also revealed that reasoning ability was the most effective predictor to academic achievement of chemistry students while emotional intelligence was the less effective predictor to academic achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions were drawn: that all the three independent variables; reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity had positive relationship with academic achievement of students. Also all the independent variables (reasoning ability, emotional intelligence and memory-capacity) were good predictors to academic achievement of chemistry students in North-Central Colleges of Education, Nigeria.

Recommendations

From the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Students of all level should be exposed to emotional intelligence, reasoning ability and memory-capacity skills in re-addressing students with academic problems.
2. Acquiring reasoning ability skills should be the priority of chemistry students in Colleges of Education since they operate at formal operational level. This could improve their academic achievement through engaging in things like puzzling or games which could improve learning principles of logical thinking.
3. Research evidence and benefits of emotional intelligence, reasoning ability and memory-capacity could be made available to science educators and publishers so that learning materials could be modified to accommodate emotional intelligence, reasoning ability and memory-capacity skills where necessary.

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